

Utilizing Sentiment Analysis for Effective Product Recommendation Based on User Feedback

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Abstract—The purpose of this study is to utilize Natural Language Processing (NLP) for accurate and real-time sentiment analysis. Sentiment analysis involves the identification of emotions such as positivity, negativity, or neutrality in text data, and is commonly known as opinion mining. This technique systematically extracts and analyzes subjective data using text analysis and NLP. Sentiment analysis has applications in various fields such as marketing, customer service, clinical medicine, and others to assess feedback, social media content, and healthcare materials. This paper focuses on sentiment analysis of service-based feedback, where users' emotions are analyzed to determine their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with a product. By examining user feedback, it is possible to quickly determine their emotional state and the reasons for it.

Keywords:Sentiment Analysis, TextBlob, Flask, Naive Bayes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding client sentiment is more important than ever in the fiercely competitive e-commerce market of today. E-commerce platforms can benefit from sentiment analysis by analyzing client feedback and suggesting areas for development. By analyzing user feedback, businesses can understand which aspects of their products are resonating with customers and which ones need improvement. Furthermore, sentiment analysis can help identify potential issues before they become larger problems. For example, if multiple users report a problem with a product, e-commerce platforms can address the issue quickly and prevent further negative feedback. By leveraging the power of sentiment analysis, e-commerce platforms can provide a better user experience and ultimately increase sales.

In addition to improving customer satisfaction and identifying areas of improvement, sentiment analysis can also help e-commerce platforms push products with positive feedback. By identifying products with high positive sentiment, e-commerce platforms can strategically market and promote those products to potential customers. Additionally, sentiment analysis can help identify customers who are likely to be brand advocates, and target them with personalized marketing campaigns. Overall, leveraging sentiment analysis can help e-commerce platforms make data-driven decisions and ultimately drive revenue growth.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

According to K. Yogeswara Rao et al [1] the importance of recommendation systems in handling the large amounts of data that are generated in the current era. It highlights the use

of item-based cooperative filtering recommendation algorithms, which are widely used, and how they help find similarities between users to recommend items based on similar users. However, the increasing number of users and items poses a challenge in finding advice lists for each user. The article proposes using Map Reduce approach and distributing the work to computer clusters to enhance efficiency. Additionally, it explores the challenges that traditional recommended systems face and highlights item-based cooperative filtering techniques that can quickly produce high-quality recommendations for large-scale problems. Finally, it discusses the importance of social influence and individual preferences in online behavior prediction and how probabilistic matrix resolution techniques can be used to fuse them in latent space for salable recommendation systems..

According to Marion Neumann et al [2], The article suggests using sentiment analysis to analyze students' emotions and feedback in real-time for large computing courses. The approach has several benefits, including ease of data collection and analysis, real-time feedback, and availability of free-form textual feedback. The authors conducted a study to assess the feasibility and usefulness of this approach, and the results showed that it can effectively capture students' emotions and feedback, helping instructors provide personalized help and adjust their teaching routines. Overall, the article provides a framework for implementing sentiment analysis to improve the learning experience of diverse student populations.

Dehbi Fatma et al. [3] N-gram features are a technique in NLP for analyzing text data by counting the frequency of co-occurring sequences of N words. Word embedding are another widely used technique in NLP that involve representing words as high-dimensional vectors that capture their semantic meaning. These embedding can be used in a wide range of NLP tasks, such as text classification, sentiment analysis, and machine translation..

Gayatri Khanvilkar1 et al [4], Sentiment analysis identifies the attitude of customers in their comments, and can classify emotions and opinions into polarity. Recommender systems use content-based or collaborative-based approaches to suggest products to users, and sentiment analysis is becoming more important in making recommendations based on users' sentiment

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

○ Preprocessing Methods

The feedback extracted from database will undergo preprocessing, which involves various steps like stemming, converting to lowercase, removing stop words, and tokenization. Tokenization involves breaking the text into meaningful components or tokens, such as words or phrases. Stop words, which are frequently used in texts but are not related to a specific subject, like conjunctions and prepositions, will also be removed. Additionally, all uppercase letters will be converted to lowercase before the classification stages. The last step in the preprocessing procedure is to determine the stem or root of derived words.

○ Feature extraction

Feature extraction refers to the process of converting input data into a set of features. Selecting the appropriate set of features is critical because they significantly impact the performance of the machine learning process. The primary objective is to transform and condense the input data into a set of representative features, also known as feature vectors, that can benefit the classifier.

○ Text Classification

Naive Bayes is used in this experiment.

A machine learning model called Naive Bayes classifier has been trained on a big corpus of product reviews to conduct sentiment analysis. A popular probabilistic machine learning approach for text categorization applications like sentiment analysis is called Naive Bayes. This simple yet efficient approach can yield good accuracy with only a little amount of training data.

The Naive Bayes method calculates the likelihood that a text will fall into one of the three sentiment categories—positive, negative, or neutral—based on the frequency of specific words and phrases in the text.

. A dataset of products reviews that has been labeled as either favourable or negative is used to train the model. The model gains the ability to correlate specific words and phrases with either positive or negative emotion during training.

A. Overall Design

The objective of this paper is to develop a sentiment analysis system that can effectively recognize user emotions. The system is capable of analyzing vast amounts of feedback data. To create the system, the researchers utilized the Python modules TextBlob and Flask. TextBlob is a natural language processing tool that enables operations like sentiment analysis and spelling checks. The system utilizes the Naive Bayes algorithm to classify feedback as positive, negative, or neutral based on sentiment.

The prerequisites software & libraries for the Sentiment analysis system are:

- Python (3.10.4)
- Flask (1.0.2)
- TextBlob

● NLTK

B. Techniques Used

(i) Naive Bayes:

A popular probabilistic machine learning approach for text categorization applications like sentiment analysis is called Naive Bayes. With just a modest quantity of training data, this simple yet powerful technique can achieve great accuracy.

The pre-trained Naive Bayes classifier used by TextBlob to analyze sentiment determines the likelihood that a given text falls into one of the three sentiment categories (positive, negative, or neutral) based on the frequency of specific words and phrases. During training, the classifier learns to associate certain words and phrases with positive or negative emotion based on their frequency in the massive corpus of product reviews that have been categorized as positive or negative.

If certain words and phrases are present, the incoming material can be categorized as good, terrible, or neutral by training the classifier. The classifier uses word and phrase frequency to determine the category to which the text most likely belongs and assigns it accordingly.

Each word or phrase in the text can be differentiated from all other features, hence the term 'Naive' in Naive Bayes. This assumption facilitates calculations by enabling the algorithm to handle a large number of attributes with only a small amount of training data.

Despite its simplicity and naive premise, Naive Bayes is a powerful algorithm that can attain high accuracy in various text classification problems.

The pre-trained Naive Bayes classifier from TextBlob is a highly-liked option for sentiment analysis projects because it does well on various benchmarks for sentiment analysis. It might not always be the greatest option for sentiment analysis jobs because the context and domain of the text being analyzed can affect how accurate it is.

IV. RESULT

The study described the aims to use natural language processing (NLP) techniques to predict emotions from text data, specifically to analyze user feedback and determine whether it is positive or negative. The proposed system then uses this analysis to produce a rating for the product based on the feedback it has received.

The system can determine which goods have received the highest customer ratings by doing this analysis of customer feedback, and it may then use this knowledge to increase sales of those products. A system might, for instance, highlight a product as a best-seller on a company's website or recommend it to other consumers if it routinely receives favorable ratings.

In this situation, NLP may be used to process massive amounts of text data and extract crucial information from them. It is imperative to remember that NLP techniques could result in false positives or false negatives and are not always correct. It is crucial to fairly assess the system's

performance and account for any biases or potential errors that might occur.

The examples that follow serve as an explanation of how to determine the sentiment score of textual feedback.

Example Feedback1: This is an awesome product,worth every penny.

Negative : No negative

Positive : Awesome.

Score: 0-1 = 1 (Positive)

1) Example Feedback2: Quality of the product should be improved.

Negative words: improved

Positive words:No positive words

Score: 1-0 = 1 (Negative)

fig 3.1.1 Rating

id	pname	price	category	description	stock	image	image2	image3	date	discount	rating	negative
17	Apple iPhone 14	899	mobile	Apple iPhone 14 128GB (Product) RED	15	iphone14redcover.png	iphone14img2.png	iphone14img3.png	2023-03-06	3	4	1
39	APPLE MACBOOK PRO	2500	laptop	mkgg3hn-a-thn-and-light-laptop-apple-original-ma	0	mkgg3hn-a-thn-and-light-laptop-apple-original-ma			0000-00-00	2	3	1

fig 3.1.2 Result in Database

Product Name	Price	positive review	negative review
Apple Iphone 14	899	4	1
APPLE MACBOOK PRO	2500	3	1

fig 3.1.3 Result

fig 2: Workflow of the system

V.CONCLUSION

In order to improve product ratings and boost sales, a study intends to create a system that analyzes sentiment. They intend to create a mobile application that can analyze sentiment in text data from any language, making it available to a wide range of people. In order to make better decisions and increase customer happiness, organizations may find this to be a beneficial tool for understanding client opinions and preferences. The application's accessibility across many platforms can aid in expanding its audience and gaining perspectives from around the globe. The study may enhance how companies collect and analyze customer input, resulting in better goods, services, and client interactions.

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